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D3.4 – Policy Brief 1

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Term
RE4GREEN	Research Ethics and Integrity for the GREEN Transition
RE&RI	Research Ethics and Research Integrity
R&I	Research and Innovation
ERA	European Research Area
EC	European Commission
ECEIA	European Conference on Ethics and Integrity in Academia
ENRIO	European Network of Research Integrity Offices
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
DNSH	Do No Significant Harm
UNDRIP	United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
CARE	Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics (Principles for Indigenous Data Governance)
LINKS	Local and Indigenous Knowledge Systems (UNESCO Programme)
WP	Work Package
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
R&I	Research and Innovation
PRACC	Practical Challenges of Climate Change: Intergenerational Justice and Freedom
EU	European Union
AI	Artificial Intelligence

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the development and dissemination of the first RE4GREEN policy brief, titled "Embedding Environmental and Climate Ethics in Research: Six Recommendations for Institutions." The brief addresses a significant and urgent gap in how research ethics and research integrity (RE&RI) frameworks account for environmental and climate concerns in the context of the green transition.

Grounded in the findings of Deliverables 1.1 (RE4GREEN, 2025a) and 1.3 (RE4GREEN, 2025b), the policy brief outlines clear, actionable recommendations for academic and research institutions to align their RE&RI governance with sustainability, justice, and precautionary principles. It targets institutional actors such as university leaders, ethics committees, curriculum developers, and researchers, providing them with guidance to reform governance structures, research strategies, training programmes, and academic curricula.

The development of the brief followed an iterative methodology, combining evidence from research with stakeholder engagement and validation. It was presented at the European Conference on Ethics and Integrity in Academia (ECEIA) 2025 and refined through input from RE4GREEN's Stakeholder Advisory Board and a joint policy workshop with the PRACC project. At the time of writing this deliverable feedback is also collected from the workshops conducted in the context of WP2. These engagements underscored the need for conceptually clear yet inclusive ethical governance, institutional accountability, and operational guidance.

This deliverable not only documents the process and outputs of Policy Brief 1 but also reflects on the lessons learned to inform the development of future briefs. It concludes with an outlook on Policy Brief 2, which will explore the protection of scientific integrity in climate-related research and will be disseminated at the ENRIO Congress in September 2025.

Introduction

Europe's transition to a sustainable future depends on research and innovation (R&I) that are ethically grounded, socially just, and environmentally responsible. However, existing Research Ethics and Research Integrity (RE&RI) frameworks have not kept pace with this transformative agenda. Most institutional and policy-level RE&RI mechanisms overlook environmental and climate concerns, fail to provide operational guidance, and place excessive responsibility on individual researchers while ignoring systemic and institutional dimensions.

The RE4GREEN project responds to this critical gap by developing recommendations to embed environmental and climate ethics into RE&RI governance across the European Research Area. As part of this effort, Task 3.4 of the project is dedicated to producing a series of thematic policy briefs, aimed at shaping responsible research practices that support the green transition.

This deliverable, D3.4, introduces the first in this series of policy briefs, titled "Embedding Environmental and Climate Ethics in Research: Six Recommendations for Institutions.". It addresses institutional stakeholders who play a central role in shaping the rules, structures, and cultures of academic research. Drawing on the project's research findings and validated through stakeholder engagement and expert feedback, the policy brief provides a roadmap for integrating environmental and climate ethics into research policy, training, evaluation, and education.

The deliverable outlines the methodology used to develop the policy brief, the rationale behind its recommendations, the dissemination and validation processes, and the lessons that will shape future policy work within the project.

Policy Briefs in RE4GREEN

Overview of Task 3.4

Task 3.4 is dedicated to developing and disseminating policy recommendations that strengthen R&I governance in support of the green transition. It directly responds to the overarching objective of RE4GREEN: to embed environmental and climate ethics into the policies, processes, and institutions shaping R&I across Europe and beyond.

The task addresses structural and systemic dimensions of R&I governance. Its primary focus is on engaging policy makers such as research funding organisations (including the European Commission), decision-makers responsible for setting research priorities, and institutional leaders in research-performing organisations. By targeting these actors, Task 3.4 aims to promote more ethically robust and environmentally responsive governance structures within the European Research Area (ERA).

Throughout the project, Task 3.4 will produce and disseminate four policy briefs. These will cover critical areas of concern identified through earlier tasks (notably T1.2 and T1.4), stakeholder engagement processes (Task 2.4), and ongoing analytical work (Tasks 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3). The briefs will include:

- At least one set of recommendations on **what should not be accepted or neglected** in the name of addressing environmental and climate challenges
- At least one brief presenting **strategies to uphold scientific integrity** in climate-related R&I
- Additional briefs with a specific focus on relevant ERA Policy Agenda actions, such as **Action 11** (An ERA for green transition) and **Action 12** (Accelerating the green/digital transition of Europe's key industrial ecosystems).

The approach is iterative, stakeholder-informed, and policy-responsive. Recommendations are not only drawn from research insights but also validated through consultation activities and targeted dissemination efforts. These include direct meetings with relevant stakeholders, contributions to public consultations, and presentations at key conferences.

Task 3.4 runs from Month 12 to Month 32 of the project and will be reported on through two main deliverables:

- **D3.4 (M18)** – Policy Brief 1 (this deliverable)
- **D3.5 (M32)** – Policy Brief 2

Methodology

The policy briefs developed under Task 3.4 follow a four-phase methodology designed to ensure that they are timely, evidence-based, and responsive to policy and stakeholder needs. This structured approach promotes both internal coherence across the RE4GREEN project and strong external impact through strategic dissemination.

1. Thematic scoping phase

Each policy brief begins with a thematic scoping process informed by project findings, such as (for Policy Brief 1) a systematic literature review identifying cross-cutting concepts and issues in the context of R&I and gap analyses of RE&RI guidelines, frameworks and training resources in relation to environmental and climate concerns. This research provides the evidentiary foundation and contextual understanding needed to identify timely and under-addressed policy challenges. Thematic choices are also informed by emerging developments in EU policy (e.g., the ERA Policy Agenda) and international debates.

2. Co-development phase

Once a thematic focus is selected, the co-development phase begins. Each brief is developed collaboratively, with partners assuming lead and supporting roles according to expertise and alignment with the topic (e.g., WECF on gender-related dimensions, AIT on policy implications of the Do No Significant Harm - DNSH principle). Contributions are also informed by ongoing activities in other WP3 tasks, as well as stakeholder engagement in WP2.

3. Internal review

Draft policy briefs undergo internal review within the consortium. Partners provide feedback on content clarity, consistency with RE4GREEN's objectives, and the feasibility of the recommendations.

4. Refinement, validation and dissemination

Following internal review, each brief is further refined and validated through interaction with stakeholders. This includes feedback from RE4GREEN's social labs, consultations with the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB), and public presentation at relevant conferences. These activities aim to ensure that recommendations resonate with real-world needs.

Figure 1: RE4GREEN Policy Brief Development Methodology

Policy Briefs Overview

Although Task 3.4 is still at an early stage, a preliminary plan is already in place for the development of four thematic policy briefs, even though the Grant Agreement foresees only two deliverables under this task (D3.4: Policy Brief 1 – M18, and D3.5: Policy Brief 2 – M32). These briefs are designed to translate RE4GREEN's research findings into timely, actionable recommendations for policy makers and research governance bodies. While a tentative schedule and topical focus has been defined, the content of future briefs may evolve to reflect emerging developments in the policy landscape and feedback from stakeholders.

The current roadmap includes:

- **Policy Brief 1** (the policy brief described in this deliverable)
Title: *Embedding Environmental And Climate Ethics In Research: Six Recommendations For Institutions*
Timeline: July 2025
Focus: Introduces key shortcomings in existing RE&RI frameworks and calls for the integration of environmental and climate ethics into institutional governance structures, evaluation processes, training, and curricula.
Dissemination: [ECEIA 2025](#) (June 2025)
- **Policy Brief 2**
Title: *Upholding Scientific Integrity within the R&I System in the Context of Climate Change*
Timeline: September 2025
Focus: Explores how research integrity can be protected and strengthened in climate-related R&I, addressing risks such as ethics dumping, bias, lack of inclusivity, and hidden methodological tools.
Dissemination: [ENRIO 2025](#) (September 2025)
- **Policy Brief 3**
Working Title: *Policy Brief with Focus on ERA Policy Agenda Action 11*
Estimated Timeline: Late 2025-Early 2026
Focus: TBD
Dissemination: TBD

- **Policy Brief 4**

Working Title: *Policy Brief with Focus on ERA Policy Agenda Action 12*

Estimated Timeline: Summer 2026

Focus: TBD

Dissemination: TBD

Policy Brief 1

A complete version of Policy Brief 1, including its final layout and visual design, is included in the annex at the end of this deliverable.

Policy Brief Topic

The first RE4GREEN policy brief is titled:

“Embedding Environmental and Climate Ethics in Research: Six Recommendations for Institutions”

This brief explores how existing institutional research practices can be enhanced to respond more effectively to the environmental and climate crises. It argues that RE&RI governance must evolve to include clear, operational, and justice-oriented standards that ensure research contributes meaningfully and ethically to environmental sustainability and climate resilience.

The brief positions environmental and climate concerns not as peripheral ethical issues, but as core considerations for responsible research and innovation. It identifies current gaps in RE&RI guidance, makes the case for reform, and outlines key principles and actions that should guide R&I systems in addressing these pressing societal challenges.

Rationale and Background Information

The recommendations for this first policy brief are grounded in the findings of deliverables 1.1 and 1.3.

D1.1 is a systematic literature review that analyses how environmental ethics, climate ethics, and RE&RI are conceptualised in the academic literature and whether there are cross-cutting concepts that can integrate them within R&I contexts. Key findings from this deliverable included:

- Lack of conceptual clarity and explicit definitions of the key topic areas (only 43% of reviewed studies provided explicit definitions of key terms).
- High degree of conceptual fragmentation, lack of shared understanding of the key topic areas.
- Over-representation of studies focused upon climate change at the expense of other environmental issues (e.g. biodiversity loss).
- Energy technologies and geoengineering technologies were over-represented topics.
- Significant disconnections between literature on research ethics and integrity, environmental ethics and climate ethics/climate justice
- Research ethics and integrity literatures largely disconnected from environmental issues

D1.3 conducted gap analyses in terms of addressing environmental and climate issues in RE&RI guidelines, frameworks and training resources. It includes reviews of 213 guidelines and frameworks, 255 training programmes and 95 training materials. Key findings from this deliverable included:

- Minimal mention of environmental and climate concerns.
- Superficial engagement with key themes.
- Lack of practical and stakeholder-centred guidance.
- Neglect of emerging domains.
- Lack of focus on justice-oriented approaches.
- Limited focus on risk assessment and management.
- Overemphasis on individual researcher responsibility and lack of institutional accountability.
- Complete absence of important principles.

Taken together, these findings reveal a clear and urgent need to account for the environmental and climate crises in the ethical governance of research. Despite growing political commitments to sustainability, the ethical foundations of research governance have not kept pace. There is a lack of normative clarity, institutional responsibility, and actionable guidance on how R&I systems should respond to environmental and climate challenges. These gaps risk weakening the legitimacy, and effectiveness of research efforts in addressing global environmental and climate threats. Now is a critical moment to embed environmental and climate responsibilities into RE&RI structures, while advancing justice-oriented, inclusive, and forward-looking research governance. Below are the synthesised challenges and gaps this policy brief aims to address:

Systemic governance limitations in RE&RI:

- **Conceptual fragmentation:** There is a high degree of fragmentation that seems to exist in literature in understandings of environmental ethics and justice and climate ethics and justice.
- **Lack of environmental and climate ethics integration into RE&RI:** 60% of analysed RE&RI guidelines and frameworks do not reference environmental or climate concerns at all. Where referenced (40%), these concerns are rarely operationalised into ethical guidelines or governance mechanisms. This is also reflected in the literature, where a gap between environmental & climate ethics and RE&RI was observed.
- **Justice-oriented approaches remain marginal:** While discussions of distributive, procedural, and intergenerational justice exist in environmental and climate ethics literature, they are rarely integrated into operational RE&RI frameworks.
- **Overemphasis on individual ethics, lack of institutional accountability:** Most RE&RI frameworks place ethical responsibility on individual researchers rather than institutions, funders, and research governance bodies, overlooking how these entities themselves may contribute to environmental harm through their investments, technological priorities, and institutional practices.

Thematic omissions in RE&RI:

- **Limited and unequal attention to climate and environmental issues in RE&RI:** RE4GREEN's literature review revealed a disproportionate emphasis on climate change, often neglecting other equally important issues. On the other hand, RE&RI frameworks fail to prioritise any climate and environmental issues.
- **Limited attention of RE&RI frameworks to emerging research domains and technologies with potential substantial impact on the climate and environment:** While there are discussions about energy and geoengineering technologies in the environmental and climate ethics literature, a lack of focus on such emerging research domains and technologies with potential substantial impact on the climate and environment was observed in RE&RI frameworks.
- **Lack of focus on justice-oriented approaches, Indigenous populations and disproportionately affected groups into RE&RI frameworks:** RE&RI frameworks dedicate little attention to justice-related concepts such as energy justice, participatory justice, and intergenerational justice. Furthermore, very few frameworks address the specific needs of disproportionately affected or Indigenous populations in the context of environmental and climate concerns.
- **Lack of gender perspectives and ecofeminist approaches:** Gendered dimensions of environmental and climate ethics remain largely absent from RE&RI frameworks. While ecofeminist perspectives highlight the intersection between gender oppression and environmental exploitation, these insights have not been structurally integrated into research governance.

Operational limitations in implementation:

- **Limited focus on risk assessment and management:** While some frameworks discuss environmental risks in broad terms, most do not explicitly recommend the use of environmental risk assessments or the implementation of precautionary measures.
- **Lack of ethical training on climate and environmental considerations:** While most training programmes and materials focus on scientific integrity and responsible research, few address environmental and climate ethics in practice.
- **Superficial engagement with key themes and lack of practical and stakeholder-centred guidance:** Even within frameworks that acknowledge environmental and climate issues, the engagement tends to be shallow. References to critical themes such as sustainability, biodiversity loss, climate change mitigation, and pollution are often limited to high-level statements without specific guidelines, tools, or enforceable obligations for implementation. Frameworks also largely fail to provide tailored, actionable guidance for high-impact stakeholder groups such as policymakers, industry practitioners, researchers, citizens, and communities.

Target Audience

The primary target audience for Policy Brief 1 consists of **academic and research stakeholders** who are directly responsible for shaping, implementing, and supporting RE&RI governance within universities and research institutions. This includes:

- University leadership and senior management
- Research ethics committees and integrity offices
- Research support staff and managers
- Educators and curriculum developers
- Researchers and postgraduate supervisors

These actors were selected because they hold critical roles in determining how RE&RI principles are **interpreted, operationalised, and embedded** within research governance structures and everyday academic practice. Their decisions shape institutional **policies, curricula, oversight mechanisms, training content, and research culture**.

In the context of the green transition, these stakeholders are in a unique position to embed environmental and climate ethics into institutional research strategies, ethics frameworks, and educational pathways. By targeting them, Policy Brief 1 aims to support a shift from individualised notions of ethical responsibility to more systemic, justice-oriented, and sustainability-driven governance models. The brief provides them with actionable recommendations to guide this transformation, aligned with EU policy priorities.

Furthermore, this policy brief was specifically developed with this audience in mind as it was accepted and presented at the [European Conference on Ethics and Integrity in Academia \(ECEIA\) 2025](#) which took place from 16 to 19 June 2025 in Uppsala, Sweden, and convenes exactly this community of RE&RI professionals, educators, and institutional leaders. The conference provided a timely and strategic opportunity to engage this group directly, validate the recommendations, and support uptake.

European Conference on Ethics and Integrity in Academia 2025

11th International Conference 16th –19th June 2025

Figure 2: European Conference on Ethics and Integrity in Academia (ECEIA) 2025

Figure 3: Policy Brief presentation at ECEIA 2025

Other important stakeholder groups, such as **research funders (including the EC)** and **policymakers**, will be addressed in subsequent policy briefs. These future briefs will focus on broader systemic levers for change and complement the institution-focused recommendations of Policy Brief 1.

Policy Recommendations

The following recommendations were developed as part of Policy Brief 1 and are based on the evidence generated by RE4GREEN Deliverables 1.1 and 1.3. They were designed to support academic and research institutions in integrating environmental and climate ethics into research governance structures, strategic planning, training, and curriculum development.

Rationale behind recommendation 1: Current institutional RE&RI policies rarely address environmental and climate concerns in a systematic way. Institutional frameworks must explicitly define and govern how environmental and climate ethics are integrated into research practices.

Recommendation 1: Integrate environmental and climate ethics into RE&RI policies, guidelines, and frameworks at the institutional level.

How can institutional RE&RI policies be aligned with Europe's environmental and climate commitments?

- Revise RE&RI policies to include environmental and climate ethics, with clear definitions for concepts like sustainability, environmental and climate justice, and Indigenous rights, while allowing space for multiple worldviews to avoid epistemic domination.
- Identify high-impact, high-risk research areas needing stronger ethical oversight (e.g. geoengineering, AI, critical raw materials and conflict materials mining, gene editing in biodiversity conservation).
- Align and clarify convergence of ethics governance with EU and global frameworks like the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Paris Agreement, European Green Deal, Do No Significant

Harm (DNSH), United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP, 2007), and Horizon Europe rules and in accordance with UNESCO's Declaration of Ethical Principles in Relation to Climate Change (UNESCO, 2017).

Rationale behind recommendation 2: Sustainability must not be an afterthought in research planning. It should shape strategic decisions, resource allocation, and the direction of innovation from the outset.

Recommendation 2: Integrate environmental and climate ethics into institutional research strategies and agenda-setting processes.

How can institutional research strategies reflect environmental and climate priorities?

- Include environmental and climate ethics considerations into research strategies, resource planning, and priority-setting.
 - Establish internal evaluation criteria for research proposals that assess environmental risks, trade-offs, and contributions to environmental and climate goals.
 - Foster cross-disciplinary collaboration (e.g., environmental science, engineering, ethics, political theory, law, social anthropology, and social sciences) to guide fair and sustainable transitions.
-

Rationale behind recommendation 3: Justice considerations must not be treated as secondary in research. They are essential for ensuring that all research — especially when it intersects with environmental and climate challenges — is fair, inclusive, and attentive to power imbalances.

Recommendation 3: Integrate justice-oriented approaches into RE&RI.

How can RE&RI structures address questions of justice, inclusion, and power?

- Embed justice frameworks — including intergenerational, procedural, epistemic and multispecies justice — into RE&RI governance and recognise and protect Indigenous rights guided by UNESCO's policy on engaging with indigenous peoples (UNESCO, 2018).
 - Support participatory research with communities affected by environmental degradation and climate change, and by the measures taken to address them (e.g. renewables, carbon capture, resource extraction) while embedding the CARE Principles (Carroll et al, 2020) (originally developed for Indigenous data governance): Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and Ethics.
 - Integrate gender-responsive and ecofeminist perspectives to address the gendered impacts of environmental and climate issues and to support intersectional gender justice in research.
 - Provide tools such as participatory method guidelines, co-design process templates, justice impact assessment templates, and support structures for inclusive engagement and review.
-

Rationale behind recommendation 4: Even well-designed frameworks can fail without the capacity to use them. Targeted training and cross-disciplinary collaboration are key to embedding environmental and climate ethics in everyday practice.

Recommendation 4: Strengthen professional training and capacity-building for researchers and ethics committees.

How can training and capacity-building better support environmental and climate ethics in research?

- Deliver targeted training on environmental and climate ethics, justice frameworks, and sustainability governance for researchers, support staff and ethics committees.
- Provide practical tools — like case studies, impact templates, and decision-making aids — to support ethical research design and review.
- Build cross-disciplinary capacity by connecting experts across ethics, environmental science, law, social anthropology, policy and other relevant fields to support collaborative learning and informed decision-making across sectors.

Rationale behind recommendation 5: To make this shift lasting, we must start earlier. Curricula shape the worldview and priorities of future researchers. Embedding environmental and climate ethics in education ensures long-term cultural and institutional change.

Recommendation 5: Embed environmental and climate ethics into academic education and curriculum development.

How can academic education prepare students to address environmental and climate challenges ethically?

- Integrate environmental and climate ethics into curricula and RE&RI teaching across all disciplines.
- Create modules on environmental and climate ethics that bridge ethics, sustainability, and innovation also drawing on UNESCO's LINKS programme (UNESCO, n.d.) to integrate Indigenous and local knowledge.
- Support faculty with resources, incentives, and staff development programmes to update curricula.

Rationale behind recommendation 6: When research outcomes are uncertain or their impacts not fully known, ethical governance demands caution. The precautionary principle serves as a guiding ethical principle for anticipating and addressing potential harm.

Recommendation 6: Operationalise the precautionary principle in institutional research governance.

How can the precautionary principle be embedded in research governance?

- Require researchers to assess and report potential climatic, environmental and social risks, especially for emerging or experimental technologies.

- Establish ethics committee protocols for applying the precautionary principle¹, including thresholds for triggering independent review or mitigation plans.
- Promote anticipatory governance approaches that prioritise responsibility, justice, and the avoidance of harm in conditions of uncertainty.

To further support implementation of the policy recommendations, the policy brief includes a stakeholder action table that translates the recommendations into concrete recommended actions for key institutional actors. This table aligns each stakeholder group's responsibilities with practical steps they can take to integrate environmental and climate ethics into research governance and practice. It is reproduced below as part of the deliverable.

Stakeholder action table

Table 1: Stakeholder Action Table of Policy Brief 1

Stakeholder group	Recommended actions
University leadership and senior management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandate integration of environmental and climate ethics into RE&RI frameworks and research strategies. • Establish policies requiring sustainability and ethics assessments of critical raw materials and conflict minerals used in research and procurement. • Promote interdisciplinary, participatory and just transition-focused research. • Allocate funding and resources to support ethics education and capacity-building. • Mandate environmental and climate ethics to be embedded into existing and future curricula.
Research ethics committees and integrity offices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include environmental/climate ethics and justice in review protocols and guidelines. • Apply precautionary principle (especially for high-impact/high-risk research). • Work with Biosecurity Committees to strengthen oversight of research with potential environmental or societal harm.
Research support staff and managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and disseminate tools to support assessment, participation and training. • Organise training sessions for researchers and staff. • Monitor evolving EU compliance requirements and embed them into research support systems.

¹ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=LEGISSUM:precautionary_principle

Educators and curriculum developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate environmental/climate ethics across disciplines. • Develop new dedicated environmental/climate ethics modules. • Use LINKS and CARE frameworks to incorporate Indigenous and local knowledge.
Researchers and postgraduate supervisors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt precautionary, participatory, inclusive, and responsible research methods. • Embed ethics into research supervision & evaluation, starting from project design.

Dissemination and Feedback

The development of Policy Brief 1 followed an iterative, stakeholder-informed process to ensure that the recommendations are not only evidence-based but also operational, relevant, and aligned with stakeholder needs. The draft brief was reviewed and refined through the following key validation activities:

ECEIA 2025 Conference Presentation

Policy Brief 1 was disseminated at the European Conference on Ethics and Integrity in Academia (ECEIA) 2025, held in June 2025. This conference is one of the most important European platforms for academic and research stakeholders working on ethics and integrity, making it a strategic venue for presenting the first RE4GREEN policy brief. The conference brings together university leadership, research ethics professionals, integrity officers, educators, and institutional policy-makers — aligning closely with the primary target audience of the brief.

The abstract for the presentation was co-authored by TRI, UBO, and WECF and submitted on 10 March 2025. It was accepted on 20 March 2025, and the policy brief was presented by the RE4GREEN project coordinator, University of Bonn (UBO), under the following conference topic:

Policy Development: Discussing the development and implementation of effective policies to promote and uphold ethical standards in academic and research environments.

The presentation generated significant interest. According to feedback from the coordinator, the session was well attended, and the recommendations were positively received by participants. One notable point of discussion concerned the challenge of defining concepts such as sustainability and justice within a diverse ethical and cultural landscape. Participants highlighted the importance of addressing conceptual fragmentation while allowing space for a plurality of worldviews to avoid epistemic domination. This feedback reinforces the need for conceptual clarity paired with inclusivity, which is reflected in the brief's approach to environmental and climate ethics.

Policy Workshop During the Midterm Meeting

A dedicated policy workshop was held on 24 June 2025 during the RE4GREEN Midterm Meeting at the Gustav-Stresemann-Institute in Bonn, with online participation also available. The workshop was co-organised by RE4GREEN and the German research project [PRACC \(Practical Challenges of Climate Change: Intergenerational Justice and Freedom\)](#). Its aim was to facilitate mutual exchange between the two projects, discuss their respective approaches to climate-related ethics and governance, and identify shared policy implications and challenges. Participants included members of the RE4GREEN consortium, researchers from

PRACC and Dr. Mihalis Kritikos, the Scientific Secretary of the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE) and a key voice in EU science and ethics policy. The agenda included presentations from each project, including Policy Brief 1 of RE4GREEN, followed by a panel discussion.

During the discussion, Dr. Mihalis Kritikos provided targeted feedback that was especially relevant to the future policy work of RE4GREEN. He offered several critical insights:

- He emphasised that "ethics by design" (the practice of integrating ethical principles into the design and development of technologies from the outset) must be a foundational principle in addressing environmental and climate issues in research governance.
- He warned that introducing new principles alone is insufficient. What is needed is the translation of ethical principles into actionable, operational steps that institutions can apply.
- He urged the RE4GREEN consortium to ensure that recommendations are concrete, specific, and pragmatic, with clear relevance to institutional realities and policy developments.
- He encouraged the team to connect its recommendations to the evolving legislative landscape, including the forthcoming Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) framework, and to remain aware of opportunities for policy influence.

These comments will be particularly valuable as RE4GREEN shifts its focus toward engaging stakeholders higher in the policy chain, including research funders and policymakers in upcoming policy briefs. The emphasis on operational clarity and institutional applicability aligns closely with this audience's expectations. Moreover, RE4GREEN will be well-positioned to support these engagements through the integration of forthcoming project outputs, including the enhanced environmental risk assessment tools being developed in Task 3.3, the practical RE&RI guidelines under Task 3.2, and the training materials and curricula emerging from Work Package 4. Together, these tools will ensure that RE4GREEN's recommendations are not only conceptually robust but also actionable and ready for uptake across the research and innovation landscape.

Feedback from the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB)

During a dedicated meeting on July 7th 2025, the SAB played a key role in validating the focus, framing, and recommendations of Policy Brief 1. Their feedback was instrumental in refining both the strategic direction and operational clarity of the brief.

SAB members emphasised the need for a more compelling and concise framing of the policy brief. Rather than opening with background information about the project, the introduction should communicate a stronger sense of urgency and relevance — addressing the question of "Why now?" up front. Similarly, members suggested shortening the overall length of the document, and restructuring it so that recommendations are more immediately visible and accessible to readers. Adding a reflective question before each recommendation was seen as an effective technique for drawing in the target audience and inviting critical self-assessment.

SAB members also noted that institutional stakeholders, especially research managers, are unlikely to take action unless there is alignment with funding requirements or broader research policy agendas. To enhance uptake, the brief should explicitly link its recommendations to influential frameworks such as the European Research Area Policy Agenda, Horizon Europe provisions (e.g. DNSH), and global sustainability commitments. This policy alignment would help ensure the brief is not perceived as optional or aspirational, but rather as part of an evolving set of institutional responsibilities.

One of the most substantive discussions concerned the treatment of Indigenous rights. While SAB members welcomed the inclusion of Indigenous perspectives, they advised caution in how these are framed. Specifically, it was stressed that additional requirements should not be imposed on Indigenous communities under the guise of research ethics. Instead, the emphasis should be on long-term, respectful collaboration, ongoing engagement beyond initial consent, and the recognition of Indigenous peoples as knowledge holders and research partners. The SAB encouraged greater awareness and integration of existing frameworks such as the CARE Principles (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics).

Overall, the SAB recognised the value of Policy Brief 1 in addressing a critical gap in RE&RI governance. Their feedback helped refine the document to ensure it is more actionable, sensitive to contextual complexities, and strategically positioned for policy influence. These inputs will also guide the development of future policy briefs and the implementation of stakeholder engagement activities in the next phases of the project.

Feedback from WP2 workshops

At the time of writing this deliverable, feedback is still being gathered from participant workshops conducted through WP2 Social Labs. This input will be carefully considered and integrated into the policy brief prior to its final publication.

A complete version of Policy Brief 1, including its final layout and visual design, is included in the **annex at the end of this deliverable**.

Next steps

Following the submission of this deliverable, Policy Brief 1 will be finalised and published on the RE4GREEN website. It will also be disseminated directly to key institutional stakeholders identified through a combination of consortium partners' existing networks, targeted internet searches, and ongoing stakeholder mapping activities conducted throughout the project. These stakeholders include university leadership, research ethics committees, and research managers, particularly those engaged in research governance and sustainability initiatives. Additional dissemination efforts may include sharing the brief through relevant mailing lists, professional associations, and project events to maximise reach and impact.

The iterative development process — which included internal consortium review, stakeholder consultation, and validation through the SAB and public presentations — proved particularly valuable. This feedback-driven approach will continue to guide the development of future briefs. Lessons learned from this process will inform both the content and engagement strategies of subsequent outputs, helping ensure they remain relevant, actionable, and grounded in stakeholder needs.

Policy work under Task 3.4 will continue throughout the project with the development of three additional policy briefs. The next and more immediate step is the preparation and dissemination of Policy Brief 2, which focuses on scientific integrity in climate-related research and innovation.

The second policy brief aims to emphasise the urgent need to **uphold scientific integrity** in climate change research and innovation to maintain **public trust, fairness, and credibility**. It will identify major ethical threats, including:

- **Ethics dumping** (research in vulnerable regions with weak oversight),
- **Research misconduct** (data manipulation, bias, concealed AI tools),
- **Lack of diverse and inclusive perspectives**, particularly outside the Global North.

The brief plans to argue that **equitable, open, and transparent** research is critical to developing effective and fair climate solutions. It criticizes current gaps in literature and practice—especially the dominance of Western frameworks and English-language publications—and calls for ethical responsibility in emerging technologies. Input will be received through the social lab participants from social lab 1 on **Health, Culture and inclusive society, Civil security led by EARMA** to ensure a circular approach and input from relevant stakeholders, ensuring equity.

The policy brief will be disseminated at the ENRIO Congress 2025 in September in Ljubljana, Slovenia to a wide audience. This will be done through a presentation, followed by a Q&A session to have an interaction with the audience and receive feedback. An abstract outlining the brief's focus has been submitted and accepted by the conference organisers.

Conclusion

Policy Brief 1 marks a significant milestone in RE4GREEN's effort to strengthen the ethical foundations of research and innovation systems in support of the green transition. It identifies major gaps in current RE&RI frameworks and offers six actionable recommendations aimed at embedding environmental and climate ethics into the core structures and cultures of research institutions.

The development of the policy brief followed an iterative and stakeholder-informed process that combined robust research evidence with extensive engagement and feedback. The brief was successfully disseminated and validated at the ECEIA 2025 conference, a dedicated midterm policy workshop, through consultation with RE4GREEN's SAB, and currently through WP2 workshops with social labs participants.

By targeting institutional actors such as university leadership, ethics committees, curriculum developers, and researchers, the brief seeks to move beyond individualised notions of responsibility and promote more systemic, justice-oriented, and precautionary approaches to RE&RI governance. It is grounded in RE4GREEN's earlier analytical work — including the systematic literature review (D1.1) and gap analysis of RE&RI resources (D1.3) — and aligned with broader European and international policy frameworks.

The policy work under Task 3.4 will continue with the development of three additional briefs. Most immediately, Policy Brief 2 will focus on safeguarding scientific integrity in climate-related research and innovation. This second brief will address pressing ethical risks such as ethics dumping, research bias, and inequities in knowledge production. It will be disseminated at the ENRIO Congress 2025, ensuring visibility and engagement with research integrity professionals and policymakers.

The lessons learned through the production and dissemination of Policy Brief 1 — particularly the importance of operational clarity, policy alignment, and stakeholder responsiveness — will guide the design and delivery of future outputs.

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Annex

EMBEDDING ENVIRONMENTAL AND CLIMATE ETHICS IN RESEARCH: SIX RECOMMENDATIONS FOR INSTITUTIONS

Who is this for?

This policy brief is intended for academic and research stakeholders responsible for shaping **research ethics and research integrity (RE&RI) governance, support, and education within universities and research institutions.**

These include:

- University leadership and senior management
- Research ethics committees and integrity offices
- Deans, department heads, and research directors
- Research support staff and managers
- Educators and curriculum developers
- Researchers and postgraduate supervisors

Why now?

Europe's green transition depends on research and innovation. However, most RE&RI frameworks ignore environmental and climate concerns. RE4GREEN's analysis shows that 60% of RE&RI frameworks in the European Research Area make no mention of such issues. Even where they do, guidance is vague and impractical often placing the responsibility on the shoulders of researcher while ignoring institutional accountability. As research increasingly shapes environmental outcomes — from AI to geoengineering — failing to act creates risks. These issues are not abstract or hypothetical. Research has historically contributed to environmental degradation, climate change and social injustice, often reinforcing power asymmetries, extractive practices, and systemic harm. This reality highlights the urgent need to adopt research paradigms grounded in environmental and climate ethics, justice, and precaution. **Ethics must evolve to ensure research supports, not undermines, Europe's climate and sustainability goals.**

What needs to change?

To address these gaps, we recommend **six key actions** to align research ethics with Europe's environmental and climate goals:

1. Integrate environmental and climate ethics into RE&RI policies, guidelines, and frameworks at the institutional level.
2. Integrate environmental and climate ethics into institutional research strategies and agenda-setting processes.
3. Integrate justice-oriented approaches into RE&RI.
4. Strengthen professional training and capacity-building for researchers and ethics committees.
5. Embed environmental and climate ethics into academic education and curriculum development.
6. Operationalise the precautionary principle in institutional research governance.

Policy recommendations

Recommendation 1: Integrate environmental and climate ethics into RE&RI policies, guidelines, and frameworks at the institutional level.

How can institutional RE&RI policies be aligned with Europe's environmental and climate commitments?

- Revise RE&RI policies to include environmental and climate ethics, with clear definitions for concepts like sustainability, environmental and climate justice, and Indigenous rights, while allowing space for multiple worldviews to avoid epistemic domination.
- Identify high-impact, high-risk research areas needing stronger ethical oversight (e.g. geoengineering, AI, critical raw materials and conflict minerals mining, gene editing in biodiversity conservation).
- Align and clarify convergence of ethics governance with EU and global frameworks like the SDGs, Paris Agreement, Green Deal, DNSH, UNDRIP, and Horizon Europe rules and in accordance with UNESCO's [Declaration of Ethical Principles in Relation to Climate Change](#).

Recommendation 2: Integrate environmental and climate ethics into institutional research strategies and agenda-setting processes.

How can institutional research strategies reflect environmental and climate priorities?

- Include environmental and climate ethics considerations into research strategies, resource planning, and priority-setting.
- Establish internal evaluation criteria for research proposals that assess environmental risks, trade-offs, and contributions to environmental and climate goals.
- Foster cross-disciplinary collaboration (e.g., environmental science, engineering, ethics, political theory, law, social anthropology, and social sciences) to guide fair and sustainable transitions.

Recommendation 3: Integrate justice-oriented approaches into RE&RI.

How can RE&RI structures address questions of justice, inclusion, and power?

- Embed justice frameworks — including intergenerational, procedural, epistemic and multispecies justice — into RE&RI governance and recognise and protect Indigenous rights guided by [UNESCO's policy on engaging with indigenous peoples](#).
- Support participatory research with communities affected by environmental degradation and climate change, and by the measures taken to address them (e.g. renewables, carbon capture, resource extraction) while embedding the [CARE Principles](#) (originally developed for Indigenous data governance): Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and Ethics.
- Integrate gender-responsive and ecofeminist perspectives to address the gendered impacts of environmental and climate issues and to support intersectional gender justice in research.
- Provide tools such as participatory method guidelines, co-design process templates, justice impact assessment templates, and support structures for inclusive engagement and review.

Recommendation 4: Strengthen professional training and capacity-building for researchers and ethics committees.

How can training and capacity-building better support environmental and climate ethics in research?

- Deliver targeted training on environmental and climate ethics, justice frameworks, and sustainability governance for researchers, support staff and ethics committees.
- Provide practical tools — like case studies, impact templates, and decision-making aids — to support ethical research design and review.
- Build cross-disciplinary capacity by connecting experts across ethics, environmental science, law, social anthropology, policy and other relevant fields to support collaborative learning and informed decision-making across sectors.

Recommendation 5: Embed environmental and climate ethics into academic education and curriculum development.

*How can academic education prepare **students** to address environmental and climate challenges ethically?*

- Integrate environmental and climate ethics into curricula and RE&RI teaching across all disciplines.
- Create modules on environmental and climate ethics that bridge ethics, sustainability, and innovation also drawing on UNESCO's [LINKS programme](#) to integrate Indigenous and local knowledge.
- Support faculty with resources, incentives, and staff development programmes to update curricula.

Recommendation 6: Operationalise the precautionary principle in institutional research governance.

*How can the **precautionary principle** be embedded in research governance?*

- Require researchers to assess and report potential climatic, environmental and social risks, especially for emerging or experimental technologies.
- Establish ethics committee protocols for applying the [precautionary principle](#), including thresholds for triggering independent review or mitigation plans.
- Promote anticipatory governance approaches that prioritise responsibility, justice, and the avoidance of harm in conditions of uncertainty.

Stakeholder action table

Stakeholder Group	Recommended Actions
➤ University leadership & senior management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Mandate integration of environmental and climate ethics into RE&RI frameworks and research strategies. ✓ Establish policies requiring sustainability and ethics assessments of critical raw materials and conflict minerals used in research and procurement. ✓ Promote interdisciplinary, participatory and just transition-focused research. ✓ Allocate funding and resources to support ethics education and capacity-building. ✓ Mandate environmental and climate ethics to be embedded into existing and future curricula.
➤ Research ethics committees & integrity offices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Include environmental/climate ethics and justice in review protocols and guidelines. ✓ Apply precautionary principle (especially for high-impact/high-risk research). ✓ Work with Biosecurity Committees to strengthen oversight of research with potential environmental or societal harm.
➤ Research support staff & managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Develop and disseminate tools to support assessment, participation and training. ✓ Organise training sessions for researchers and staff. ✓ Monitor evolving EU compliance requirements and embed them into research support systems.
➤ Educators & curriculum developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Integrate environmental/climate ethics across disciplines. ✓ Develop new dedicated environmental/climate ethics modules. ✓ Use LINKS and CARE frameworks to incorporate Indigenous and local knowledge.
➤ Researchers & supervisors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Adopt precautionary, participatory, inclusive, and responsible research methods. ✓ Embed ethics into research supervision & evaluation, starting from project design.

Evidence base for the recommendations

Research Ethics and integrity for the GREEN transition (RE4GREEN, <https://re4green.eu/>), a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project, aims to develop a European Research Area framework on ethics and integrity for research and innovation activities that supports the fair and sustainable transition. One of RE4GREEN's main objectives is to analyse the current RE&RI landscape and provide key stakeholders with actionable recommendations on integrating environmental and climate ethics into research and innovation governance.

The recommendations presented in this policy brief are grounded in RE4GREEN's analysis of RE&RI frameworks, guidelines, training programmes & materials and academic literature. The project identified significant gaps and challenges in how environmental and climate ethics are addressed in RE&RI across Europe. Key issues included:

- Systemic governance gaps: Many RE&RI frameworks lack references to climate or environmental ethics, rely too heavily on individual responsibility, and show weak integration of justice-oriented approaches.
- Thematic omissions: Emerging technologies, justice, Indigenous rights, gender perspectives, and ecofeminist approaches are rarely considered in research governance.
- Operational shortcomings: There is limited attention to environmental risk assessment, precaution, and practical guidance. Training on climate and environmental ethics is also scarce.

These gaps highlight the urgent need for structural, institutional, and educational reforms — as outlined in this policy brief.

What's next?

We recognise that the implementation of these recommendations will require time, resources, and institutional commitment. Practical constraints such as staffing, funding, and existing governance processes must be taken into account. This policy brief offers a strategic direction, but each institution must adapt its approach to local realities and capacities. To support the implementation of these recommendations, RE4GREEN is developing operational RE&RI guidelines, to be published in 2026, which will offer practical support for embedding environmental and climate ethics into research governance and practice across institutions.

But guidance alone is not enough. What universities and research institutions choose to prioritise today will shape the role of research in either deepening or preventing environmental harm. We must move beyond statements of intent and begin transforming the foundations of how research is governed, taught, and evaluated. *We have a responsibility to ensure that research does not reproduce the very injustices it aims to address.*

Further reading

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2. RE4GREEN. (2025). Gap analysis of research ethics and integrity resources for R&I in general and new climate and environmental technologies in particular (Deliverable 1.3). Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101131706. <https://re4green.eu/deliverables/>

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Environmental Ethics	A branch of philosophy that considers the moral relationship between humans and the natural world, focusing on responsibilities toward ecosystems, non-human species, and the planet as a whole.
Climate Ethics	A field that examines the ethical dimensions of climate change, including responsibility for emissions, fair distribution of impacts and adaptation burdens, and duties to future generations.
Justice-Oriented Approaches	Research and governance strategies that explicitly address inequalities, power dynamics, and the distribution of risks and benefits, especially in relation to climate and environmental issues.
Climate Justice	A concept that recognises the uneven causes and effects of climate change and seeks equitable solutions, particularly for groups and individuals disproportionately affected by climate impacts.
Environmental Justice	The concept that all people, regardless of race, income, or geography, should have equal protection from environmental harms and equal access to environmental benefits.
Energy Justice	A concept that aims to ensure fair access to energy, equitable distribution of energy costs and benefits, and recognition of affected communities in energy decision-making.
Intergenerational Justice	The concept that current generations have responsibilities toward future generations, particularly in preserving environmental and social conditions that support life and well-being.
Procedural Justice	A dimension of justice concerned with the fairness and inclusiveness of decision-making processes, particularly involving affected or marginalised stakeholders.
Epistemic Justice	The ethical concept emphasising fairness in whose knowledge is valued, included, and recognised in research, especially for historically marginalised groups.
Multispecies Justice	A principle that recognises the rights, interests, and well-being of non-human species, promoting fair and respectful relationships between humans, animals, and ecosystems in research and decision-making.
Indigenous Rights	Legal and moral rights of Indigenous peoples, including the right to self-determination, land, culture, and to be involved in decisions affecting their environments and livelihoods.
Precautionary Principle	An approach to risk management, where, if it is possible that a given policy or action might cause harm to the public or the environment and if there is still no scientific agreement on the issue, the policy or action in question should not be carried out.
High-Impact / High-Risk Research	Research that may have significant environmental, societal, or ethical consequences due to its scale, uncertainty, or the technologies involved (e.g., geoengineering, synthetic biology).
Sustainability (in the research context)	A commitment to conducting and supporting research in ways that meet current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs, including attention to environmental, social, and economic impacts.
Ecofeminism / Ecofeminist Perspectives	An approach that links ecological concerns with feminist insights, highlighting how systems of domination and exploitation of nature are connected with the oppression of women and marginalised groups.
Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)	An EU principle requiring that research and innovation must not cause significant harm to any of the EU's environmental objectives, such as climate mitigation, biodiversity protection, or pollution reduction.
Participatory Research/Co-design	Research approaches that involve affected communities and stakeholders as active participants in defining research questions, processes, and outcomes.
Emerging Technologies	Technologies that are in early stages of development and may have uncertain, large-scale, or long-term effects on society or the environment (e.g., AI, geoengineering, gene editing).

